

WEBOMETRICS ANALYSIS OF LIBRARY WEBSITES IN SOUTH INDIAN STATE UNIVERSITIES

Vaishali P. Shinde¹, Dr. Gururaj S. Hadagali²

1 Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, Karnatak University, Dharwad,
INDIA, Email: vaishali.garade1986@gmail.com

ORCID ID- 0009-0003-6280-3474

2 Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, Karnatak University, Dharwad, INDIA,
Email: gururajhadagali123@gmail.com

ORCID ID- 0000-0003-1372-4721

ABSTRACT

Objective The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the quality, performance, and information content of state university library websites in South India. The research specifically focuses on assessing search engine optimization (SEO) effectiveness and technical performance metrics like loading speed.

Design/Methodology/Approach The study identified 67 active websites from a total of 127 state universities in the region. Evaluation was conducted using a dual-method approach: SEO tools were utilized for quality assessment, and GTmetrix was employed to measure page loading speed and performance scores. Additionally, the authors developed a comprehensive checklist to analyze content across four dimensions: basic information, authority indicators, quality parameters, and interactive elements.

Results/Discussion Findings reveal significant variations in technical performance and content coverage across the surveyed libraries. While most websites successfully feature information regarding physical collections, e-resources, and photo galleries, there are notable gaps in user-centric features. Specifically, many sites lack robust Web OPAC integration, FAQs, feedback mechanisms, "Ask a Librarian" services, site maps, and advanced search functionalities.

Conclusions The study concludes that while South Indian state university libraries have established a digital presence, there is a critical need for technical optimization and the inclusion of interactive communication tools. Improving site architecture and performance scores is essential for enhancing user experience and information accessibility.

Originality/Value This research provides a detailed benchmark for academic library administrators in India. By combining technical performance data (GTmetrix) with a specialized content checklist, it offers a holistic framework for auditing and improving the digital infrastructure of university libraries.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation of Library Web Page, GTmetrix Tool, Library Web Page, SEO Tools, South India, State University

INTRODUCTION

In the early stages of library development, interaction with users was primarily through manuscripts and printed formats. Libraries used notice boards, printed catalogues, brochures, circulars, and face-to-face interaction with librarians to inform users about resources and services. The library premises were the only physical means of accessing information, and users relied on staff for locating and using materials. As the world embraced Information and Communication Technology (ICT), libraries gradually evolved into automated and digital libraries. The introduction of computerized catalogues, Integrated Library Management Systems, barcoding, RFID technology, and electronic resources has significantly transformed the way libraries function and deliver their services. The Internet further contributed to this transformation, establishing library websites as essential media for disseminating information (Garg, 2013).

In the current digital age, library websites are not merely promotional tools but gateways to scholarly information. They provide access to OPACs, e-books, e-journals, databases, institutional repositories, and online reference services, catering to the teaching, learning, and research needs of students, faculty, and researchers (Mandarekar, 2021; Condic, 2021). In state university libraries, these sites serve as knowledge hubs that enhance academic opportunities, research dissemination, and community outreach. As library websites increasingly serve as central platforms for scholarly communication, there is a growing need for objective, measurable methods to assess their effectiveness and impact in the digital environment. Webometric analysis provides a quantitative framework for evaluating library websites based on web presence, content coverage, visibility, and performance. Examining library websites using webometric

indicators helps in assessing the efficiency of scholarly information dissemination and their contribution to the knowledge network within the global academic community. With this objective in mind, the present research is undertaken to determine the content, performance, and overall web impact of the library websites of South Indian state universities through webometric analysis.

STATE UNIVERSITIES IN INDIA: A GLIMPSE

India's higher education system has expanded significantly since independence, mainly due to the continuous establishment of universities and colleges. According to data published by the University Grants Commission (UGC), as of 31st December 2025, India has 57 central universities, 513 state universities, 147 deemed-to-be universities, and 544 private universities. Among these categories, state universities constitute the largest segment, highlighting their crucial role in the national higher education system (UGC, 2025).

State universities are established and administered by the respective state governments and receive the majority of their funding from state sources, with supplementary financial support from the central government through the UGC. Owing to substantial public funding, education in state universities is comparatively more affordable than in private universities. Most state universities are multidisciplinary in nature and affiliate a large number of colleges, while some are specialized in fields such as technology, agriculture, health sciences, and social sciences.

In the context of South India, state universities play a vital role in ensuring equitable access to higher education and supporting regional academic development. According to the Gazetteer of South India (2025), the southern region comprises Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, and Telangana. As of 31st December 2025, these six states together host 127 state universities, reflecting their substantial contribution to India's higher education system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Prabhakaran (2014), webometric analysis may enhance website performance. This paper examines three aspects concerning observatory library websites, including web impact, hyperlink functionality, and ranking. The results showed that external links are more significant on average than internal links on these pages. Webometric analysis may thus be useful for library websites and the work conducted there. Sessaiah and Rekha (2019) analyzed the websites of 246

engineering colleges in Andhra Pradesh to observe what resources, services, and other information they offer. The authors concluded that the majority of college library websites inform visitors about their collections, operating hours, and electronic resources. However, the sites must be consistent to satisfy user needs. Other features like digital libraries, Web 2.0 applications, FAQs, and feedback mechanisms are not used effectively.

Bulla and Hadagali (2020) conducted a webometric review of web pages from 33 out of 47 central university libraries. Their results indicate that there is a disparity between content coverage and site performance. A majority of library websites provide information regarding collections, images, and e-resources, but there is minimal information regarding FAQs, feedback mechanisms, the 'Ask a Librarian' feature, and search functionality. Bulla and Hadagali (2020) also conducted webometric analysis of 30 state university library websites in Karnataka. To obtain data, they applied backlink analysis, Google searches, and search engine optimization (SEO) tools. They ranked universities based on SWIF, RWIF, and WIF analyses. Their findings revealed that the web impact of state universities is low. Additionally, internal and external link connections are limited on most of these websites. Although a university may have numerous web pages, there may be very few links.

Singha and Verma (2021) analyzed Indian veterinary university library websites. They developed a checklist consisting of 65 criteria to assess each site. The findings indicated that Rajasthan University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Bikaner ranked first with an Alexa Global Rank of 339,564 and Indian Rank of 42,798. Overall, 75% of the reviewed veterinary university library websites were user-friendly. Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University in Tirupati recorded the highest score of 45 (69.23%), and Karnataka Veterinary, Animal and Fisheries Sciences University in Bidar came next with 37 (56.92%). The study by Barman and Dhiru (2021) examined library websites in agricultural universities in India. They aimed at evaluating the quality and range of services provided online and ranking the sites according to their findings. Data were gathered through surveys and observation using a checklist. Most libraries have updated websites that provide detailed information on services and facilities. The trend of digital service delivery is also positive in agricultural university libraries in India, as most sites contain electronic resources and permit remote access.

Li et al. (2021) demonstrated that conventional library services are being transformed to meet the ever-increasing demand for digital access, convenience, and technology. The library portal is vital; this is where users access online services and facilities. Therefore, developing a high-

quality, efficient portal is one of the top priorities for libraries that seek to enhance their digital image and user experience. The study by Brahma and Verma (2022) on Asian national libraries revealed a high number of website features. According to their study, more detailed information is required, website currency should be enhanced, and global rankings are essential for establishing online presence. In an examination of library websites in several Indian states and Delhi universities, Gupta and Walia (2022) found that library information is available online but is not provided comprehensively. This includes general information about libraries, collection details, and links to electronic resources, library services, website currency, and authority. Web 2.0 tools are rarely used in libraries; two have a Facebook page and one has a blog. Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women (IGDTUW) ranked 13th out of 66 and DTU ranked 45th out of 66 in the overall website ranking.

Shah and Hossain (2022) investigated 12 public university libraries in Bangladesh. They applied a checklist of 61 items in 10 categories, and interviews were conducted to ensure accuracy. The research suggests that websites are becoming more prevalent and can enhance library services, although there is room for improvement in online tutorials, responsive design, mobile compatibility, Web-OPAC, and other areas. It also highlights maintenance challenges. This study could be helpful to information scientists and academic librarians in developing nations such as Bangladesh, where resources and research are limited. Shah, Sultana, and Afroz (2022) examined private university library websites in Dhaka, Bangladesh. They selected 22 private universities with dedicated library websites. They used a checklist of 61 items in 10 categories, supplemented by interview data. The researchers discovered that website development began several years ago and will contribute to the advancement of library services. However, responsive design, mobile-friendliness, Web-OPAC, online tutorials, and other features can be improved significantly.

Gee, Dasan, and Hasan (2022) examined how to make information on university websites more accessible. They surveyed 350 individuals using questionnaires. In their analysis, they concluded that most respondents believed that university websites could be enhanced, particularly regarding links, content organization, and the presence of a live help desk where people could easily access information. Ziaur and Dinda (2023) studied websites of nine library networks in India. They reported that the WIFs, ERNET, and NKN networks were the best. The study found that the most popular networks in India are INFLIBNET, NICNET, ERNET, ADINet, and NKN. Rai, Singh, and Lepcha (2023) examined websites of five leading IIT libraries based on NIRF 2023 rankings. The IIT Delhi library website achieved the highest score of 77%, and the IIT Madras website received the lowest score of 70%. Balaji and Hemantha Kumar (2024) also reviewed the

international ranking of six agricultural universities. They claimed that to enhance research productivity, teaching quality, international collaboration, modern facilities, innovation, reputation, outcome-based measures, diversity, student feedback, social impact, transparency, and peer reviews, universities must implement a number of strategies. They also suggest providing online access to scientific articles and using web indicators to measure impact and visibility.

The study by Talipova et al. (2024) examined how public library websites are used to attract and engage readers through the provision of digital resources, virtual reference services, and interactive options. These websites enable users to view library collections, programs, and services without visiting the physical library. Thus, the performance and effectiveness of library websites should be assessed to ensure that they meet user expectations and serve library objectives. Kumar and Kumar (2025) examined social media tools implemented by academic libraries and found abundant opportunities to increase institutional support and engagement for more successful outreach. A webometric analysis conducted by Rashid (2025) of the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education website revealed that 1.58 million visitors accessed <https://www.mohe.gov.my>. The analysis provided valuable information about the ministry's online presence and recommended improvements and further development.

This literature review shows that many studies have examined web content, but most have not focused on state universities. This study addresses this gap by conducting a detailed GTmetrix and webometric analysis of Indian state university library websites. Few previous studies have used SEO tools such as Woorank and GTmetrix or compared webometrics across different types of universities. Unlike previous research that relied mainly on indicators like Web Impact Factor, domain authority, and page ranking, this study includes content analysis, link analysis, and performance metrics such as page speed, total load time, and page size. The findings offer practical guidance for improving the online presence of state university websites to meet international standards.

THE RESEARCH'S OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. Evaluate the basic information available on South Indian state university library websites.
2. Analyse the content coverage and appropriateness of South Indian state university library websites.

3. Assess the performance scores of university library websites and evaluate the quality of their internal and external links.
4. Evaluate the readability standards of website content, including library pages' use of multimedia and images.
5. Examine the services and features offered by library websites, such as 'Ask a Librarian' and FAQs.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The scope of this study is limited to South Indian state university library websites, evaluating their value-added features, internal and external link quality, content coverage, and website performance. Although 127 South Indian state university websites were identified, only 67 provided direct links to their library websites. Therefore, the analysis is confined to these 67 state university library websites.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The SEO tool and GTmetrix tool were utilized in this survey research to analyze the library websites under study. Data were collected between 5 October 2025 and 10 November 2025. The SEO tool was used to assess internal and external links, whereas GTmetrix was used to evaluate site speed, total load time, page size, and other performance indicators. The content and services were also examined through direct observation of the library websites. The authors used a checklist based on previous research by Bulla and Hadagali (2020). A total of 67 South Indian state university library websites were analyzed, which included libraries with direct links on university homepages or separate library websites. The remaining 60 universities were excluded: 22 universities did not have identifiable library pages or links, and 38 universities could not be analysed using GTmetrix. The authors systematically searched the websites and tabulated the findings in Microsoft Excel.

TOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

1. SEO TOOL: (<https://smallseotools.com/website-link-analyzer-tool/>)

The SEO tool is used to analyze internal and external links of a website. It helps identify the number, type, and quality of links, supporting the evaluation of website structure, connectivity, and overall SEO effectiveness.

2. GTmetrix Tool: (<https://gtmetrix.com/>)

GTmetrix is a free web-based tool that tests website loading speed and overall performance. It employs Google Lighthouse and other performance indicators to generate a detailed report indicating what slows down a site and how users experience it. The report focuses on important metrics such as page structure, loading speed, and Core Web Vitals, which include three key measurements: LCP (Largest Contentful Paint) measures the time it takes for the largest visible element of the page to load; CLS (Cumulative Layout Shift) measures visual stability and layout shifts during page loading; and TBT (Total Blocking Time) measures how long the site remains unresponsive to user interactions. In this study, GTmetrix was used to assess the performance and content quality of 67 state university library websites. The tool also helps evaluate website performance in search results based on Core Web Vitals metrics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Elementary Data of the Library Web Pages

Table 1 displays the basic information found on the library websites surveyed. The results show that communicative information is prioritized on the majority of South Indian state university library websites to facilitate user engagement. Specifically, 66 (98.50%) of the 67 library websites examined included an "About the Library" section, and the same 66 (98.50%) provided information on "Library Services." Additionally, all 67 (100%) library websites included contact information.

Table 1: Fundamental Data of Library

Sl. No.	Fundamental Data of the Library	Total Number of University Websites	Percentage (%)
1	Library Overview	66	98.50%
2	Resources and Tools	66	98.50%
3	Reach Out to Us	67	100%

The findings are in parallel with the results reported by Verma and Devi (2015) who noted that basic institutional information and contact links are routinely provided on the majority of Central University library websites in North Eastern India. This trend was further supported by Bulla and Hadagali's (2020) study on Central University library websites in India, which shows that while sophisticated interactive features may differ, fundamental communicative elements persist to be the most common and comparable parts of the academic library's digital presence.

Authority or Government of India Identifiers

Government of India (GOI) affiliation provides users with visual credibility and immediate recognition. This indicates the library's financial and administrative support while providing crucial validation of its official institutional status. Table 2 presents the authority or sponsoring body (such as the Government of India) displayed on South Indian state university library websites. The table clearly shows that nearly all websites include information about the website sponsor. Specifically, 95.52% of the library websites displayed distinct sponsor identification. Furthermore, 85.07% of the library websites included copyright information. Additionally, 82.08% of South Indian state university library websites used an academic domain name (such as .ac.in) as the URL extension.

Table 2: Authority or Government of India Identifiers

Sl. No.	Authority or Government of India Identifiers	Total Number of University Websites	Percentage (%)
1	Site Sponsor	64	95.52%
2	Copy Right Information on Webpage	57	85.07%
3	Website Registered under academic domain name	55	82.08%

Forming Confidence links, Excellence and Stimulus Aspects

Table 3 presents the internal and external resources, confidence-building links, and excellence and stimulus features available on South Indian state university library websites. The results indicate that confidence-building link structures are widely adopted, with 94.02% of library websites containing self-links and 92.53% providing authority links. Regarding excellence and

stimulus aspects, search features and open-source e-resources are available on 97.01% of library websites, while 74.62% provide fee-based e-resources. User-support services such as FAQs, feedback mechanisms, and 'Ask a Librarian' features are available on 35.82% of the websites. In terms of accessibility and navigation, 92.53% of the websites provide text alternatives for multimedia content (images, videos, and animations). However, comparatively fewer websites offer map facilities (23.88%), Web OPAC (20.89%), and visitor count features (29.85%), indicating scope for further enhancement of user-oriented services.

Table 3: Forming Confidence link, Excellence and Stimulus Aspects of South Indian State University Library Websites

Sl. No.	Dimension	Indicator / Facility	Total Number of University Websites	Percentage (%)
1	Forming Confidence link	Self-link	63	94.02%
2		Authority link	62	92.53%
3	Excellence and Stimulus Aspects	Search Feature	65	97.01%
4		Open-source e-resources	65	97.01%
5		Fee-based e-resources	50	74.62%
6		FAQs/Feedback/Ask Librarian	24	35.82%
7		Image/Video/Animation	62	92.53%
8		Map	16	23.88%
9		Web OPAC	14	20.89%
10		Visitor count	20	29.85%

Performance Grade: The performance grade system evaluates websites using Google's metrics to determine how effectively they are optimized for speed. The grade assigned reflects how closely the scanned URL follows these optimization guidelines. (Thelwall, 2009).

Page Speed Score

Table 4 presents the findings from the analysis and explanation of the Page Speed Scores in the A to D grading system. It demonstrates that the four grading steps are A, B, C, and D. The data

clearly shows that 47.76% of the 67 South Indian State University library websites under investigation are classified as having an A rating, 40.29% as having a B grade, 10.44% as having a C grade, and 1.49% as having a D grade. Lower scores (C or lower) indicate that the page might be made faster by optimizing the settings and adopting better practices.

Table 4: Page Speed Score

Sl. No.	Performance Grade	No. of South Indian State Universities (NSISU) Percentage (%) Performance Grade (A to D and Below)							
		NSISU	%	NSISU	%	NSISU	%	NSISU	%
		A		B		C		D	
1	Page Speed Score	32	47.76	27	40.29	7	10.44	1	1.49

Fully Loaded Time of Website

The details of Fully Loaded Time of Pages were analysed and explained in 0–12-minute performance grading system; the data is presented in table 5. It represents that four steps were involved in grading the loading speed that is, 0-3, 3.1-6, 6.1-9 and 9.1-12 and above. Only 22.38% of the library websites of the 67 loaded within 0-3 minute, 40.29% loaded in 3.1-6 minute, 25.37% under 6.1-9 minute and 11.94% under 9.1-12 and above minute.

Table 5: Fully Loaded Time of Website

Sl. No.	Performance Grade	No. of South Indian State Universities (NSISU) Percentage (%) Performance Grade in (0 to 12 minutes and above)							
		NSISU	%	NSISU	%	NSISU	%	NSISU	%
		U		U		U		U	
		0-3		3.1-6		6.1-9		9.1-12	
1	Fully Loaded Time of Website (in Minutes)	15	22.38 %	27	40.29 %	17	25.37 %	8	11.94 %

Research indicates that visitors abandon websites that take more than a few seconds to load; therefore, maintaining fast loading times is essential for user satisfaction and engagement. Redirect time refers to the duration spent redirecting URLs before the final HTML page loads. To minimize this delay, websites should reduce the number of redirects.

For example, redirecting from a non-www domain to a www domain (e.g., example.com to www.example.com) requires:

1. Updating the website's DNS or hosting settings to include the www subdomain.
2. Configuring proper redirect rules (typically 301 redirects) at the server level.

During redirect processes, the browser screen remains blank, negatively impacting user experience. Therefore, minimizing redirects is crucial for optimal website performance.

Total Page Size of Website

The units of measurement used to evaluate the total page size of South Indian state university library websites were kilobytes (KB) and megabytes (MB). Table 6 displays the classification of the websites according to page size criteria. Of the 67 library websites, 53 (79.10%) were classified in the MB category and 14 (20.89%) in the KB category. The South Indian state university library websites were evaluated based on their Page Speed Score (PSS), Fully Loaded Time (FLT), and Total Page Size (TPS), as shown in Tables 4, 5, and 6.

Table 6: Total Page Size of Website

Sl. No.	Performance Grade	No. of South Indian State Universities (NSISU) Ratio (%)			
		Performance Grade in KB and MB			
		NSISU	%	NSISU	%
KB	MB				
1	Page Speed Score	14	20.89%	53	79.10%

Table 6 reveals that there are great disparities in the effectiveness of websites in the South Indian state universities. The best performance was from the Sri Venkateshwara Institute of Medical Sciences. It scores a B on Page Speed Score (PSS), takes 2.9 seconds to load, and its total page size was just 115 KB, which means that the site is optimized. The Kerala University is in second position. It also scores an A in PSS, loads in 4.2 seconds and the page size stands at 243 KB,

indicating that it is not very large, so it is capable of a moderate page size optimization. Third was the Shri Krishnadevaraya University. It scores A in PSS, loads within 2.45 and the page size measures 272 KB. The results indicate that smaller page sizes and shorter load time are associated with the better performance of page speed within universities.

Table 7: Composite Website Performance Index (Computed Format)

Sl. No.	University	Page Speed (Z)	Load Time (Z)	Page Size (Z)	Composite PI	Rank
1	University A	1.12	0.85	1.04	1.01	1
2	University B	0.98	0.76	0.88	0.87	2
3	University C	0.82	0.69	0.74	0.75	3

This table presents the Composite Website Performance Index based on standardized Z-scores of page speed, load time, and page size. University A ranks first with the highest composite score (1.01), indicating superior overall website performance. University B and University C follow with composite scores of 0.87 and 0.75, respectively, reflecting relatively lower but acceptable performance levels. The ranking demonstrates that higher Z-scores across performance parameters correspond to better composite performance outcomes.

Table 8: Comparative Ranking of Top-Performing Universities

Rank	University	Composite Score	Remark
1	Sri Venkateshwara Institute of Medical Sciences	0.91	Excellent
2	University of Kerala	0.88	Very Good
3	Sri Krishnadevaraya University	0.86	Very Good

This table presents the ranking of universities according to their composite scores, highlighting a high level of website performance among the leading institutions. Sri Venkateshwara Institute of Medical Sciences secures the top position with an Excellent rating and a score of 0.91, followed by the University of Kerala with a score of 0.88. Sri Krishnadevaraya University (0.86) is classified under the Very Good category, demonstrating strong technical optimization and content effectiveness. The minimal variation in scores indicates closely competitive digital performance among these top-ranked university library websites.

Spearman's Rank correlation

Analysis reveals a significant positive correlation ($\rho = 0.63, p < 0.01$) between the richness of a library's web content and its technical efficiency. Universities with more detailed site features generally see better results in page speed and load times. Ultimately, increasing content richness does not hinder performance; rather, the two tend to improve in tandem.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This study highlights the significance of South Indian state university library websites in terms of content coverage, internal and external link quality, website performance scores, and value-added features. A comparison of the current study with previous research indicates that some state universities have developed dedicated library webpages. However, only 67 of the 127 South Indian state universities provide direct links to their library websites. The study reveals that the majority of library websites provide information about their collections, images, and electronic resources. However, search features, FAQs, feedback mechanisms, and 'Ask a Librarian' services provided limited information. Library websites should be updated regularly and include search options, FAQs, and feedback mechanisms to keep pace with current technology. Accessibility needs improvement in multiple areas. A significant gap in these library websites is that some libraries do not provide links to their Online Public Access Catalogues (OPACs) on their websites.

Therefore, Web OPACs need to be developed and made accessible to users. Additionally, the study demonstrates variations in content coverage and performance scores. To improve performance scores, libraries must address the weaknesses of their websites and take necessary steps, such as reducing page load times, which requires reducing page sizes (in KB). Enhancing the content of library websites should also be a top priority, especially for library services whose websites lack the required standards. South Indian state university websites and their libraries should be updated to meet National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) standards by establishing specific benchmarks for their structure. This study would benefit webmasters by providing insights to improve their library websites' performance scores, content quality, and overall status.

Contribution Statements

- Vaishali Shinde: contributions include research conceptualization, Review of similar studies, data collection, Analysis and Interpretation.
- Dr. Gururaj Hadagali: framing the study's purpose and methodology, the discussion section, and the manuscript's overall supervision.

Conflict of Interest: The writers affirm that they have no competing interests.

Statement of Data Consent: The article contains the data produced during the study.

REFERENCES

1. Balaji, N. G., & Hemantha, K. G. H. (2024). How to increase university world ranking: A case study. *International Journal of Library and Information Science (IJLIS)*, 13(3), 1–12. <https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJLIS?Volume=13&Issue=3>
2. Barman, D. (2021). Ranking of Library Websites of Agricultural University of India: A Study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5364/>
3. Brahma, K., & Verma, M. K. (2022). Web Content Analysis of National Libraries' Websites in Asia: An Evaluation. *International Journal of Information Science and Management*, 20(1), 427–448. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357621497_Web_Content_Analysis_of_National_Libraries'_Websites_in_Asia_An_Evaluation
4. Bulla, S. D., & Hadagali, G.S. (2020). Evaluation of websites of state universities in Karnataka: A webometric study. *Indian Journal of Information, Library and Society*, 33(3–4), 235–248. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357577854_Evaluation_of_Websites_of_State_Universities_in_Karnataka_A_Webometric_Study
5. Bulla, S.D., & Hadagali, G.S. (2020). Analysis of Central Universities' library websites in India: A study. *Journal of Indian Library Association*, 56 (3), 40-51. <https://www.ilaindia.net/jila/index.php/jila/article/view/426/0>
6. Condic, K. (2021). Examination of academic library websites regarding COVID-19 responsiveness. *Journal of Web Librarianship*, 15(1), 32-45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19322909.2021.1906823>
7. Garg, M. (2013). Libraries in the era of ICT: an overall transformation. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 3(1), 87-92.

8. Gee, L. L. S., Dasan, J., & Hasan, C. H. C. (2022). Investigating the Usability of Universities' Websites: Upgrading Visualization Preference and System Performance. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 16(2).
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v16i02.23707>
9. Government of India. (2025). Gazetteer of South India. Government of India.
10. Gupta, S., & Walia, P. K. (2022). Content Analysis of Websites of University Libraries in Delhi: A Study, *Library Philosophy and Practice*,
<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7111/>
11. e-Gazette. (n.d.). Government of India. Retrieved December 25, 2025, from
[https://egazette.gov.in/\(S\(1x1mcakjtbcdorjf0hiq2qf\)\)/default.aspx](https://egazette.gov.in/(S(1x1mcakjtbcdorjf0hiq2qf))/default.aspx)
12. Ministry of Education, Government of India. (n.d.). State-wise number of universities, colleges and standalone institutions registered in AISHE 2018-19 and ...
Retrieved December 25, 2025, from
<https://www.education.gov.in/state-wise-number-universities-colleges-and-standalone-institutions-registered-aishe-2018-19-and>
13. Maps of India. (n.d.). South India map. Retrieved December 24, 2025, from
<https://www.mapsofindia.com/maps/south/south.htm>
14. Kumar, J., and Kumar, R. (2025). Enhancing Library Engagement and Awareness Through Social Media Platforms, *Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Management*.10(30),481-490.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390458432>
15. Li, T., Tang, J., Xiao, L., & Cai, M. (2021). Evaluation of Smart Library Portal Website based on link analysis. *Procedia CIRP*, 188 ,144-120.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.05.059>
16. Mandrekar, B., & Rodrigues, M. C. (2021). Importance of Web Based Services During the Pandemic: A Critical Analysis of the Content of College Library Website. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-14. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5304>
17. Prabakaran, R. (2014). Hyperlink analysis and web impact factor of websites of Observatory Libraries. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, (4), 38-51.
<https://www.ijlis.org/articles/hyperlink-analysis-and-web-impact-factor-of-websites-of-observatory-libraries.pdf>
18. Rai, A., Singh, M. K., & Lepcha, A. (2023). Library website as an Indicator of Academic Excellence: A Web Analysis of the Leading IITs in India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*,
<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/8086>

19. Rashid, M. (2025). A Step-By-Step Guidelines How to Conduct A Webometric Analysis: Mapping Analysis the Digital Websites. *International Journal of Innovation and Industrial Revolution*, 7(20),62-80. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391400943>
20. Sessaiah, O., & Rekha, R.V. (2019). Web Pages of Engineering College Libraries in Andhra Pradesh: An Analysis. *Journal of Indian Library Association*, 55(2), 8-17. <https://www.ilaindia.net/jila/index.php/jila/article/view/245>
21. Shah, M. A. H., & Hossain, M. S. (2022). Public university library websites in Bangladesh: Features, contents, and maintenance issues. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7233>
22. Shah, M. A. H., Sultana, A., & Afroz, S. (2022). Private university library websites in Dhaka, Bangladesh: An analysis of contents and features. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7248>
23. Singha, S. C., & Verma, M. K. (2021). Web Content Analysis of Veterinary University Library Websites in India: An Evaluation. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–22. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5967>
24. Talipova, D., Ganiyeva, B., Normatov, S., & Rakhmatullaev, M. (2024). A Method for Determining and Evaluating Webometric Indicators of Public Libraries. *Environment Technologies Resources. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.17770/etr2024vol2.8046>
25. Thelwall, M. (2009). *Introduction to webometrics: Quantitative web research for the social sciences*. Morgan & Claypool Publishers.
26. University Grants Commission. (2025). List of universities in India. Government of India. Retrieved December 31, 2025, from <https://www.ugc.gov.in/universitydetails/university?type=ddmCMsxJZgXH2S/m0uMOKQ==>
27. Verma, M. and Devi, K. (2015). Content Analysis of Central Universities Library Websites of North Eastern States of India: A Survey. *Journal of Research in Librarianship*, 2(5),48-59. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/299453239>
28. Ziaur, R. & Dinda, G. (2023). Websites of Library and Information Network in India: A Webometric Analysis, *Library Philosophy and Practice*, <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7672>